

UDHAKAVAHA SROTAS: A CRITICAL REVIEW OF AYURVEDIC AND MODERN PERSPECTIVES

Dr. Ashwini B. Raut^{1*}, Dr. Kalpana Raje², Dr. Syamlal S.³

¹MD 3rd Year Scholar,

²MD (Ayu), Professor & HOD,

³MD (Ayu), Assistant Professor,

Department of Rachna Sharir, Institute of Teaching and Research in Ayurveda, Jamnagar.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Ashwini B. Raut

Dr. Ashwini B. Raut, Department of
Rachna Sharir, Institute of Teaching
and Research in Ayurveda, Jamnagar.

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ABSTRACT

Srotas are considered one of the fundamental concepts in Ayurveda and represent the channels responsible for transportation, transformation, nourishment, and elimination in the body. Among various Srotases, Udhakavaha Srotas is specifically concerned with the maintenance and transportation of water and body fluids. Classical Ayurvedic texts describe its Moolasthanas as Tala and Kloma and explain that its vitiation leads to Trishna, Mukhashosha, and even Sadyomarana. The present review aims to compile and analyze the classical references related to Udhakavaha Srotas and correlate them with contemporary concepts of fluid metabolism, dehydration, and thirst mechanism. Ayurvedic understanding of Udaka and Kledata demonstrates the importance of fluid balance in maintaining normal physiological functions. Modern science explains fluid regulation through intracellular and extracellular

fluid compartments, hypothalamic osmoreceptors, and vasopressin secretion. The review highlights the close similarity between Ayurvedic and modern concepts related to water metabolism and homeostasis. Thus, Udhakavaha Srotas can be considered an important physiological entity responsible for hydration, nourishment, and survival.

KEYWORDS: Udhakavaha Srotas, Trishna, Udaka, Fluid Metabolism, Ayurveda, Dehydration.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of Srotas is one of the most fundamental theories in Ayurveda. Understanding the concept of Srotas is challenging because it is closely related to both the anatomy and physiology of the human body. Acharya Charaka mainly considered functional abnormality and Acharya Sushruta considered structural abnormality. Ayurveda classics proclaim “Srotomayam hi Shariram”^[1] that is the living body is a channel system that carries Dosha, Dhatu, Upadhatu and Mala which are the basic building elements of the body.^[2] The channels of circulation which carry the dhatu transforming to their destination are called as Srotas. The vitiation, depletion, and maintenance of existed bodily structures are never possible without Srotas. The physiological and anatomical pathways that carry all the components, elements, signals, reflexes come under Srotas.

Several words are used to describe “Srotas”.^[3] In various hymns of Vedas mentioned as Asrava, Sira, Pantha, Srotya, Antra, Dhamani, Gavini, Nadi, Kha, and Snawani. All these words mean Srotas only and it is predominately constituted by Akasha Mahabhoota, hence Srotas are also called “Kha” meaning Akasha.

Review of Literature

Concept of Srotas

Etymology

Shabdhakalpadruma

“Srotah, klee, sravateeti | sru gatau + srureebhyam tat cha”

The term Srotas is originated from the main root “Sru” meaning ‘having Gati’ with kli pratyaya and sruri with tat pratyaya.^[4]

Amarakosha

“Srotas (napum) | aktrimajalavahanam”

Srotas has been defined as “Akrutimajalavahanam” meaning the natural pathway through which movement of fluid takes place by itself.^[5]

Charaka Samhita

Acharya Charaka explains Srotas in detail, their classification and functional aspects in Srotovimanam chapter; the term Srotas is defined as “Sravanaat Srotamsi”, i.e., the structure through which Sravana Kriya takes place.

Sushruta Samhita

Sushruta has described in detail the number, types, and functions of Srotas in the Dhamani Vyakarana Adhyaya. He has mentioned eleven pairs of Srotas and distinguishing features of Srotas with Sira and Dhamani.^[6]

Ashtanga Sangraha

Acharya Vagbhata has stated that innumerable Srotases are present in the body and the whole body is made up of minute channels. The orifices of Srotas resemble lotus stalks through which nourishment is carried to all parts of the body.^[7] Vagbhata classified Srotas into Bahya and Abhyantara Srotas.^[8]

Definition and Importance of Srotas

The word Srotas denotes channels, paths, orifices, and passages.^[9]

The pathway that helps transformation of substances is called Srotas.

Nutrient substances are supplied to cells and tissues through Srotas.^[10]

Channels carry transformed dhatu to nourish tissues.^[11]

Srotases are empty spaces spread throughout the body.^[12]

No component of Purusha can undergo Kshaya or Vriddhi without Srotas.^[14]

Millions of Srotases are present in the body.

Synonyms of Srotas

Srotamsi

Sira

Dhamani

Rasayani

Rasavahi

Nadya

Panthana

Marga

Sariracchidra

Samvrtasamvrta

Sthana

Asaya

Niketa

Kha^[15]

Structure of Srotas

Acharya Charaka states that Srotas possess color similar to the Dhatu present within them. They are branched like capillary networks and may be circular, large, small, or elongated resembling leaf venation.^[16]

Acharya Sushruta described Khani (pores) in the walls of Dhamani similar to minute passages in lotus stems through which Rasa is transported throughout the body. Vagbhata used the term “Dwara” instead of “Kha”.^[17] Sushruta further described that Srotases originate from organ cavities and spread throughout the body transporting Rasadi Dhatu.^[18]

Types of Srotas

According to Sushruta, Srotas are of two types^[19]

1. Bahirmukha Srotas
2. Antarmukha Srotas

According to Charaka, Abhyantara Srotas are thirteen in number.^[20]

Udhakavaha Srotas

Udhakavaha Srotas are the channels responsible for transportation and maintenance of water within the body.^[21]

“Udhakavahanam Srotasam Taalu Moolam Klomam Cha”

According to classical references, Taalu and Kloma are considered the Moolasthanas of Udhakavaha Srotas.^[22,23]

Causes of Vitiations of Udhakavaha Srotas^[24]

- Exposure to excess sunlight
- Ushna Vihara
- Ama Dosha
- Fear
- Alcohol consumption
- Excess intake of dry food
- Suppression of thirst

Features of Vitiation of Udhakavaha Srotas^[25]

- Dryness of tongue
- Dryness of palate
- Dryness of lips
- Dryness of Kloma
- Excessive thirst

According to Sushruta, injury to Udhakavaha Srotas leads to severe thirst and immediate death.

Viddha Lakshana of Udhakavaha Srotas^[26]

- Pipasa
- Sadyomarana

Charaka considered Udhakavaha Srotas second in order after Pranavaha Srotas, whereas Sushruta considered it third.^[27,28] This difference reflects the physiological emphasis of Charaka and the anatomical-surgical approach of Sushruta.

Udaka Pramana

Ayurveda describes the quantity of water in the body as ten Anjali.^[29]

Physiology of Udhakavaha Srotas

Srotases are responsible for nourishment of all Dhatus. Similarly, Udaka is an essential component supplied externally and distributed internally through Udhakavaha Srotas. Kledata is the effect produced by Udaka and is essential for digestion and physiological functioning.

Various diseases producing Trishna include

Jwara

Atisara

Visuchika

Grahani

Arshas

Pandu

Chardi

Raktapitta

Kamala

Prameha

Jalodara

Shotha

Gulma

Visharoga

Hikka

Swasaroga^[30]

Trishna

Trishna is an integrated aspect of Udhakavaha Srotas. Vata and Pitta vitiation leads to depletion of Rasa and Udaka causing Mukhashosha and excessive thirst. Ayurveda considers Trishna both as physiological and pathological process maintaining fluid balance.^[31]

Sadyomarana

Vitiation or injury to Udhakavaha Srotas may result in Sadyomarana. Disturbed fluid metabolism causes altered osmotic pressure, reduced plasma volume, impaired circulation, and early cellular death.

Modern Review

Fluid Metabolism

Modern physiology states that approximately 70% of body weight consists of fluid divided into

1. Intracellular Fluid (ICF)
2. Extracellular Fluid (ECF)

Intracellular Fluid

ICF constitutes around 40% of body weight and contains water, proteins, potassium, magnesium, and phosphate.^[32]

Extracellular Fluid

ECF includes plasma and interstitial fluid. Regulation of osmolarity depends on vasopressin secretion and thirst mechanism controlled through hypothalamic osmoreceptors.^[33]

Dehydration

Dehydration occurs when fluid loss exceeds intake resulting in reduction of extracellular fluid volume. Severe dehydration can lead to shock and death.^[34]

Thirst Mechanism

Thirst is controlled by the hypothalamus. Increased plasma osmolarity stimulates osmoreceptors resulting in thirst sensation and vasopressin secretion.^[35,36]

DISCUSSION

The concept of Srotas represents an extensive physiological transport system responsible for circulation, nourishment, and elimination. Udhakavaha Srotas specifically regulates water metabolism and maintenance of body fluid equilibrium. Ayurvedic descriptions of Trishna, Mukhashosha, and Sadyomarana correlate remarkably with modern concepts of dehydration, osmotic imbalance, and circulatory failure.

The Moolasthanas of Udhakavaha Srotas, namely Taaalu and Kloma, indicate structures associated with thirst perception and fluid regulation. The classical symptoms of Udhakavaha Srotodushti such as dryness of tongue, palate, and excessive thirst resemble manifestations of dehydration and electrolyte imbalance described in modern medicine.

The role of hypothalamic osmoreceptors and vasopressin secretion in modern physiology parallels Ayurvedic understanding of Trishna regulation. Ayurveda recognizes Udaka as an indispensable factor for digestion, tissue nourishment, and survival. The concept of Kledata closely resembles fluid-mediated biochemical and metabolic activities. Hence, the classical understanding of Udhakavaha Srotas provides a comprehensive physiological and pathological framework relevant even in contemporary clinical practice.

CONCLUSION

Udhakavaha Srotas is an important physiological entity described in Ayurveda responsible for maintenance, transportation, and regulation of body fluids. Classical Ayurvedic literature elaborates its Moolasthanas, functions, symptoms of vitiation, and clinical importance in detail. The symptoms of Udhakavaha Srotodushti such as Trishna, Mukhashosha, and Sadyomarana closely resemble dehydration and fluid-electrolyte imbalance described in modern science.

Modern physiological concepts including intracellular and extracellular fluid balance, osmoreceptors, hypothalamic thirst center, and vasopressin regulation demonstrate remarkable similarities with Ayurvedic concepts of Udaka and Trishna. Therefore,

understanding Udhakavaha Srotas through both Ayurvedic and modern perspectives provides a better insight into fluid metabolism and maintenance of homeostasis in the human body.

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